

ENA Webin-CLI Data Submission Practical

As we have discussed, there are three routes of submission:

- Interactive
- Programmatic
- Webin-CLI

In this exercise, you will have the opportunity to submit a set of raw read data to the test version of the **ENA Webin-CLI submission** service.

Webin Submissions Portal (TEST): <https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

You will need an ENA Webin account to use for this exercise. Webin accounts can be registered on the webin portal 'Register' page:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/accountInfo>

The screenshot shows the 'Webin Submissions Portal' registration page. At the top, there is a header with the ENA logo and the text 'EUROPEAN GENOME-PHENOME ARCHIVE Webin Submissions Portal'. Below the header, the page is titled 'Account Management'. The main content area is titled 'Account Details' and contains several input fields for registration: 'Abbreviated center name', 'Full center name', 'Laboratory Name', 'Address', 'Country', 'Password', and 'Confirm Password'. At the bottom of the form, there is a section for 'Contact Information' with a link to 'Add At Least One Contact' and a checkbox for 'No Sensitive Data' with the text 'I confirm that the data submitted through this account is NOT sensitive, restricted-access or human-identifiable.'

It will be helpful to review how the metadata model works. You can find an overview of this here:

[Metadata Model](#)

Throughout this exercise, you are asked to use the ENA test service, which allows you to make submissions which will be removed after 24 hours. If you're not sure if you're in the

test server, you can check the address in your browser which will begin 'wwwdev' rather than 'www':

<https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>

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The Scenario

You have sequenced a sample derived from soil metagenome in an attempt to identify denitrifying bacteria. You will be submitting a set of paired read data files obtained as a result of sequencing to the ENA test submission service. This is identical to the production submission service, but submissions are retained for <24 hours. It's therefore perfect for training settings like this.

Since you will be using Webin-CLI to only submit your data files, the study and sample registration will be done interactively.

The Study

To begin, you should **register a study**. Recall that a study describes the purpose of the work you have done, groups other objects beneath it, and controls when the data becomes public. A study is required for all submissions to ENA.

1. Log in to the Webin test submission service with your account ID and the password:
<https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/>
2. After logging in, find the 'Studies (Projects)' tab and click on the '**Register study (project)**' button to see the study registration interface:

3. Set a **release date** for your study (this is when all data associated with the study will be released). This needs to be between now and a maximum of 2 years in the future.
4. The '**Study Name**' field should be filled in with something brief and meaningful that can help you find and recognise the study.
5. You should take time to provide a descriptive title and informative abstract for your own studies, but these can be edited later if needed. The title could be something similar to:
Study of Soil Microbiome from <Your Town/Lab>
6. When you have completed all required fields, click '**Submit**' and then confirm.

7. Now back on the main page, navigate to the 'Studies (Projects)' tab and click on the '**Studies Report**' button to see the study you just registered. You might need to refresh the page.

Make a note of its accession numbers, which will resemble:

ERP##### and **PRJEB#####**

Note: For a real submission, these would be the numbers you would cite in any publications involving the data.

The Sample

The next step is to register the sample, which will give other users essential context for the sequence data you are submitting. The sample describes the source biological material of your sequencing work.

In ENA, samples are required to conform to a checklist of values. Checklists define a set of mandatory and recommended values for a given type of sample. It is recommended that you look at these early and make sure you collect all required metadata items for the type of sample you will be registering.

The selection of available checklists can be browsed at:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/checklists>

1. Return to the main page of the Webin Portal and find the 'Samples' tab.

<https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/>

2. Click on the '**Register samples**' button.
3. Expand the section '**Download spreadsheet to register samples**'. You must choose an appropriate checklist of values to be provided for your sample. Browse the range of checklists available.

Note: Please make sure you use a MlxS checklist (Environmental checklist) for metagenomic data.

4. Which samples checklist do you feel is most relevant for the sample you have sequenced?
5. Submitters now have the option of including additional fields in their checklist. It is not necessary to include any additional fields but you can take this opportunity to see which fields are included as mandatory, recommended and optional, what requirements they have, and what else is available.

Click '**Next**' when you're ready.

6. Download the TSV template and open the file in Excel on your computer.

Please note that you should submit your spreadsheet in the same format that you have downloaded it (TSV).

7. When you open the TSV template, the 3rd row will state "#units". Please keep this row intact and enter your data from the 4th row as shown below. This is important for the system to successfully parse your tsv file:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K
1	Checklist										
2	tax_id	scientific_name	sample_alias	sample_title	sample_description	project name	collection date	geographic location (latitude)	geographic location (longitude)	broad-scale environmental context	local environmental conte
3	#units							DD	DD		
4	xxxxx	soil metagenome	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx	xxx
5											
6											
7											
8											
9											

8. Find the appropriate taxon for your sample: to reiterate what we discussed during the presentation, please use a taxonomy that is as specific as possible. In this case for example, “**soil metagenome**” instead of “**metagenome**”.

- a. This can be looked up on our rest API. Here is an example of a search for “metagenome”. You can search for the relevant taxonomy by replacing “metagenome” in the url below:

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/taxonomy/rest/scientific-name/metagenome>

You can also search for the species name to find its tax ID on the NCBI Taxonomy database.

- b. NCBI Taxonomy database:

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>

9. Give a 'Unique name' to your sample (sample_alias)

This value must always be unique among all samples submitted by your account and is a way for you to locate and recognise your specific samples.

10. Give your sample a title, this could look something like:

Soil metagenome sample from <Your Town/Lab/Location>.

11. Write a brief description for your sample

12. Fill out the remaining details.

Tip: You can always find out more about what a field means and what information it accepts by going back to the checklist fields page on the Webin Portal and reading their description and validation.

Collection date format (year-month-date): 2024-10-24 , 2024-10 , 2024

13. By the time you have completed this, your sample will be well-annotated and understandable to people finding it in the database later. Click on ‘**Upload filled spreadsheet to register samples**’ on the Register Samples page and upload/submit the spreadsheet.

14. Now back on the main page, navigate to the 'Samples' tab to see the sample you just registered. You might need to refresh the page.
Make a note of its accession numbers as you will need these later:

ERS#####

The Read Data

Now that study and sample metadata have been registered, it is time to upload and submit the read data you have produced. In this scenario, you have produced a set of paired fastq files:

- readfile_R1.fastq.gz
- readfile_R2.fastq.gz

These are the raw read data files you have obtained as a result of sequencing your sample.

Submit Read Read Data using Webin-CLI

The final step is to register the read data produced by sequencing. This will be done using the Webin-CLI program.

NOTE: You will require [Java version 17 or newer](#) for this exercise. If you do not have it on your computer, please install it.

Please have the [latest Webin-CLI version](#) installed.

1. Enter the following command on the terminal:

```
$ java -jar webin-cli-8.1.1.jar -help
```

This will output the list of options which can be used with this program. Explore these options to see how the program runs.

2. Now that you have had a look at the program, let's look at the FASTQ files you'll be submitting. There are two FASTQ files you have produced.

- readfile_R1.fastq.gz
- readfile_R2.fastq.gz

Ensure you are in the correct directory:

```
$ cd file/path
```

3. Next, you must have a manifest file. This file performs three functions:

- Indicates the names of files to submit
- Describes experimental metadata
- States the study and sample the data belong to

The ENA now accepts manifest files in TXT format and JSON format. TXT format is less likely to encounter format errors but if you are confident with JSON file format and would like to give it a try, please go for it. Please prepare your manifest file in one of the below formats:

'reads_manifest.txt'

```
STUDY TO DO
SAMPLE TO DO
NAME TO DO
INSTRUMENT TO DO
INSERT_SIZE 200
LIBRARY_SOURCE TO DO
LIBRARY_SELECTION TO DO
LIBRARY_STRATEGY TO DO
FASTQ TO DO.fastq.gz
FASTQ TO DO.fastq.gz
```

'reads_manifest.json'

```
{
  "study": "TO DO",
  "sample": "TO DO",
  "name": "TO DO",
  "instrument": "TO DO",
  "insert_size": "200",
  "library_source": "TO DO",
  "library_selection": "TO DO",
  "libraryStrategy": "TO DO",
  "fastq": [
    {
      "value": "TO DO.fastq.gz",
      "attributes": {
        "read_type": ["paired"]
      }
    },
    {
      "value": "TO DO.fastq.gz",
      "attributes": {
        "read_type": ["paired"]
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

4. The manifest file is a list of tag-value pairs. Please create the file and fill out the fields missing (labelled as 'TO DO') from the manifest file:

- STUDY: enter an accession for the study you registered earlier (PRJEBxxx)
- SAMPLE: enter an accession for the sample you registered earlier (ERSxxx)
- NAME: give the experiment a unique name

- LIBRARY_SOURCE: [Check permitted values for library source](#)
- INSTRUMENT: [Check permitted values for instrument model](#)
- INSERT_SIZE 200
- LIBRARY_SELECTION [Check permitted values for library selection](#)
- LIBRARY_STRATEGY [Check permitted values for library strategy](#)
- FASTQ: enter the name and file path of the first sequence file
- FASTQ: enter the name and file path of the second sequence file

5. Now you have everything you need to submit your sequence data, it's time to check whether your submission is valid. Again, fill in the incomplete sections in the command below labelled as 'XXX':

```
$ java -jar webin-cli-8.1.1.jar -context reads -manifest  
(manifest file name).txt -userName Webin-XXX -password XXX  
-test -validate
```

Note: The -validate command will only check if all is good with your files. It will not submit the files. This is a good command to use when you want to make sure your files are correct and everything is in place before you proceed to submit them.

6. Finally, it's time to submit the sequence files, so complete the following command and run it:

```
$ java -jar webin-cli-8.1.1.jar -context reads -manifest  
(manifest file name).txt -userName Webin-XXX -password XXX  
-test -submit
```

7. The program will notify you as it successfully validates the files and uploads them to ENA. You will then be provided accessions for your experiment and run objects. Note these down and your submission is complete.

Return to the interactive Webin interface and view the sample and run tabs to see the objects you submitted today: <https://wwwdev.ebi.ac.uk/ena/submit/webin/login>